

DAMAGE TOLERANCE ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED REPAIRS TO COMPOSITES STRUCTURES

C. H. Wang^{1*}, J. Y. Goh¹, J. Ahamed¹, A. Glynn² and S. Georgiadis²

¹School of Aerospace, Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

²Boeing Research & Technology Australia, Melbourne, Australia

* Corresponding author (chun.wang@rmit.edu.au)

A damage tolerance methodology is developed to predict the strength of bonded repairs containing manufacturing flaw or in-service damage. A series of experiments have been carried out using specimens with varying disbond lengths to investigate the effect of pre-existing flaws on the load-carrying capacity of scarf joint. The experiments show a considerable reduction in strength with an increase in disbond length, greater than the reduction in bond area. Computational models using the cohesive zone technique have been employed to predict the strength of scarf joint containing pre-existing flaws. The hybrid cohesive-interfacial model has been found to provide good correlation with the experimental tests, providing a promising technique for damage tolerance analysis of scarf repairs.

Keywords: *Composite repair, damage tolerance, cohesive zone model*

1. Introduction

Airworthiness certification of adhesively bonded scarf repairs remain a significant challenge due to the lack of non-destructive inspection techniques that are capable of detecting weak or kissing bonds. Currently no structural credit is given to bonded repairs for safety-critical or primary aircraft structures, which must be able to sustain design loads *without* repairs. In other words, repairs are assumed to be fully ineffective when performing structural integrity assessment. This approach limits the application of the bonded repair technology to largely secondary structures or primary structures with negligible damages.

To overcome the aforementioned challenge, it is necessary to develop a damage tolerance assessment methodology for bonded structures to demonstrate compliance with airworthiness standards [1]. In this approach a disbond is assumed to exist along the adhesive bond; the disbond size is set by the detection limit of approved non-destructive inspection techniques. This approach has two major implications on the design and certification of repairs. Firstly, repairs need to be designed to sustain the design loads in the presence of disbonds. Secondly, a validated damage tolerance analysis methodology is required to predict the complex

growth behaviour of pre-existent disbonds in bonded repairs.

This paper presents an experimental and numerical analysis of the damage tolerance behaviour of adhesively bonded scarf joints. Additional experiments were carried out to characterise the fracture properties pertinent to disbonding and delamination damage, which are used to identify the fracture parameters of cohesive zone models employed to predict the load-carrying capacity of scarf joints containing embedded flaws of varying sizes.

It is found that stresses vary in the adhesive along the scarf due to different ply angles [2]. It is also found that the mode of failure along the bondline varies with respect to the lay-up angle of the bonded ply. This is due to a reduced load carrying capability in the adhesive at the 45° and 90° plies. This leads to failure in the plies. The cohesive zone model shows promises in predicting the strength reduction due to pre-existing flaws. It is found that a complex model is required to capture the complex crack branching behaviour and its stress fluctuations along the bondline [3].

DAMAGE TOLERANCE ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED REPAIRS TO COMPOSITES STRUCTURES

2. Experimental

The mode I and II fracture toughness of the composite laminate and the adhesive was measured using double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notched flexure (ENF) tests respectively. This is an element level test to obtain parameters used for the subsequent numerical analysis. Force-displacement curves were obtained from both sets of tests. The DCB tests were loaded up to a predetermined displacement and the ENF tests were loaded up to failure.

2.1. Scarf joints with embedded flaws

Composite laminates made of VTM 264 uni-directional carbon-fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) prepreg material were bevelled to form scarf angle of 5 degrees. Scarf joints were secondarily bonded using VTA260 film adhesive. Both the CFRP prepreg and the film adhesive are from the Advanced Composites Group. The test specimens were fabricated to resemble a scarf repair to a damaged structure. The scarf and repair panel have the same quasi-isotropic layup $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$.

Two types of specimens were manufactured. The first type was a scarf joint with an embedded flaw simulated by thin polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) strips of 3, 6, and 12 mm in length, referring to Fig.1. Four specimens of each flaw size were fabricated for testing, in addition to three specimens of the baseline scarf joints without flaws.

Tests were conducted under quasi-static tension until failure. The loads and machine displacements were recorded.

Fig.1. Schematic of scarf joint containing pre-existent flaws

3. Experimental Results

The scarf joint specimens were observed to have fractured by a mixture of cohesive and interfacial failure. Examples of scarf joints with a 12mm embedded PTFE and without the embedded PTFE are presented in Fig.2 and 3 respectively. It can also be seen from the bands on the specimen that intralaminar failure occurred at the 90° plies. This is due to intralaminar failure from matrix cracking through the ply.

Fig.2. Failure mode for a scarf joint with a pre-existing flaw.

Fig.3. Failure mode for a scarf joint without a pre-existing flaw.

DAMAGE TOLERANCE ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED REPAIRS TO COMPOSITES STRUCTURES

4. Cohesive Zone Model

4.1. Model theory

The constitutive equation for linear-elastic systems is

$$\sigma_i = k_i \delta_i \quad (1)$$

where σ , k and δ denote the stress, stiffness and displacement [4]. Loading mode (I or II) is denoted by subscript i . When the stresses reach a maximum value, fracture occurs at σ_i^u , which is then followed by a linear softening behaviour to a displacement δ_i^f expressed in terms of fracture toughness, G_c .

$$\delta_i^f = \frac{2G_{i,c}}{\sigma_i^u} \quad (2)$$

Eqs.1 and 2 describe the traction-separation behaviour as illustrated in Fig. 4.

In most cases, bonded joints are under mixed mode loading. Therefore, a damage initiation model based on the quadratic stress criterion is given as

$$\left(\frac{\langle \sigma \rangle}{\sigma_1^u} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma_2^u} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

Fig.4. Linear traction law for the cohesive zone model [4]

This is followed by the Benzeggagh-Kenane (B-K) fracture criterion for damage evolution given as

$$G_{IC} + (G_{IIC} - G_{IC}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right)^n = G_c \quad (4)$$

4.2. Model calibration

The cohesive element parameters were derived using an inverse method from the experimental results. Force-displacement curves were correlated between experimental and numerical analyses for the DCB and ENF tests. The parameters for the fracture strength and the fracture energies were refined in this process. An example of the calibration is seen in Fig. 5.

The properties of the cohesive zone models, with the element size being 0.5mm, are listed in Table 1. It is clear that the adhesive have a lower strength but higher fracture energies than the composites.

Fig.5. An example of cohesive model calibration on a DCB force-displacement curve

Table 1: Properties of cohesive zone models (modified)

Property	Adhesive model		Composite model	
	Tensile	Shear	Tensile	Shear
Strength (MPa)	56	58	45	85
Fracture Energy (kJ/m ²)	1.13	7.75	0.462	1.60

DAMAGE TOLERANCE ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED REPAIRS TO COMPOSITES STRUCTURES

5. Numerical Analysis

A non-linear implicit numerical analysis was performed on a two dimensional representation of the specimens. Since there was no out-of-plane effects observed during the experiments, plane strain 4-node orthogonal and 3-node triangular elements were used to model the adherends. An orthotropic material property was used to model the composite plies. Fig. 6 shows mesh refinement along the bondline. Fig. 7 shows that the adhesive is represented using four elements. The model is fixed at one end and loaded in tensile displacement at the other.

Two modelling approaches are considered. In one model, denoted as *adhesive model*, the adhesive layer is modelled using cohesive elements with the strength and fracture properties of the adhesive.

The second model, denoted as *composite model*, involves cohesive elements in the middle of the adhesive and along the composite-adhesive interfaces. The middle cohesive element was modelled using the fracture properties of the adhesive to replicate a cohesive failure. The cohesive-adhesive interface layers were modelled using a composite fracture property to model the intralaminar failure behaviour.

Fig.6. Close-up of the mesh at the bondline

Fig.7. Close-up of the mesh at the adhesive and the location of the cohesive elements for a 4mm flaw size

6. Numerical Results

The shear stress, $\tau(x)$, in the bondline, x , along the adhesive was retrieved. It is normalised by the average shear stress, $\tau(\text{avg})$, and the length of the scarf, L . It shows that the peak stresses occur at the 0° plies as shown in Fig. 8. The result of the scarf joint analysis is seen in Fig. 9. Model 1 was capable of capturing the strength of the scarf joint at small flaw sizes ($L_f < 3$ mm). However, at larger flaw sizes, the damage tolerance prediction of the scarf joint was much larger than experimental results.

Model 2 shows an improvement in the damage tolerance prediction of the scarf joint specimens. A comparison between the experimental values and the prediction from Model 2 shows a slight under-prediction at small flaw sizes ($L_f < 5$ mm) and very good correlation as the flaw sizes increases. Overall, Model 2 has shown good agreement with the experimental results.

Further analysis of the scarf joint with increasing flaw sizes ($12 \text{ mm} < L_f < 23 \text{ mm}$), shows that the size of the flaw does not affect the joint as significantly as before.

DAMAGE TOLERANCE ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED REPAIRS TO COMPOSITES STRUCTURES

Fig.8. Shear stresses along the middle of the adhesive

Fig.9. Failure mode for a scarf joint with a pre-existing flaw.

7. Conclusions

The load-carrying capacity of scarf joint has been found to decrease with the size of the initial flaw, at a rate faster than the reduction in bond area. Cohesive model using adhesive properties has been found to over-predict the joint strength, underestimating the strength reduction due to initial flaws.

Experimental observation of the failure surface reveals a mixed failure modes: cohesive failure of the adhesive at termination of 0° plies and interfacial fracture at the terminations of 45° and 90° plies. An improved cohesive zone model that incorporate the composite fracture behaviour at the composite-adhesive interface has been found to provide a very good correlation with the experimental results.

8. References

1. *Composite Materials Handbook: MIL-HDBK 17-3F*, D.o. Defense, Editor. 2002.
2. C Wang and A Gunnion, *On the Design Methodology of Scarf Repairs to Composite Laminates*. Composites Science and Technology, 2008: p. vol. 68, pp. 35-46.
3. M.F.S.F. de Moura R.D.S.G. Campilho, A.M.G. Pinto, J.J.L. Morais, J.J.M.S. Domingues, *Modelling the tensile fracture behaviour of CFRP scarf repairs*. Composites: Part B, 2009. **40**: p. 9.
4. Turon, A., Davila, G., Camanho, P., & Costa, J. (2007). *An Engineering Solution for MESH Size Effects in the Simulation of Delamination using Cohesive Zone Models*. Engineering Fractures Mechanics, Science Direct , vol. 74, pp. 1665-1682.